

IMPORTANCE OF INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES IN TERMS OF DEVELOPMENT OF TOURISM IN THE CONTEXT OF SERVICE EXPORT

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Abstract: Exports of goods and services are extremely important for national economies. Because thanks to exports, goods and services are sold to people living abroad directly or indirectly, and income is generated accordingly. If this income is directed to domestic investments, increases in production volume and economic growth occur. Due to this importance, service exports have an important share in a country's international commercial activities, and in this context, the tourism sector constitutes a significant portion of service exports. However, it is possible to say that the tourism sector has a significant difference compared to other sectors that operate for export. Although exports are generally considered as the sale of goods and services abroad, goods and services in the tourism sector are sold to foreign tourists domestically. Tourists who come to the country for various reasons benefit from the services provided by hotels and consume food and beverages in hotels. In other words, the payment made to stay in a hotel is generally made to benefit from all kinds of goods and services in the hotel, and therefore goods and services are sold to tourists in the hotel. In this respect, it is possible to say that the export of goods and services indirectly carried out by the tourism sector is carried out at lower costs because it has the advantage of transportation compared to other sectors. In order to obtain high levels of income from tourism activities, which are so important for the country's economy, it is extremely important for promotional activities and the technical features of the service. In this process, the effective use of information technologies is of great importance. In other words, information technologies (IT) provide significant contributions to the development of the tourism sector and these contributions are increasing day by day. In particular, positive developments in digitalization activities allow the level of efficiency in the tourism sector to increase, the level of accessibility to increase and customer satisfaction to be achieved.

Keywords: information technologies, development of tourism, service export, domestic investments, commercial activities.

1. INTRODUCTION

One of the most important elements of economic growth and development is the export of goods and services. Because thanks to exports, national income increases occur, income increases cause investments to increase and naturally the production volume increases. In addition, investments to be made in order to increase the export volume cause other sectors that produce goods and services in the form of raw materials and intermediate goods to take action, in other words, they indirectly affect other sectors positively. The benefits of exports in terms of economic growth are not limited to these. Export activities contribute positively to a country's foreign trade balance. In other words, the income obtained as a result of export activities is used to pay off foreign debts and finance imports, and the

foreign trade surplus to be obtained contributes to the increase in foreign exchange reserves and the financial strengthening of the country. In addition, increases in export volume encourage companies to produce on a larger scale, which in turn encourages more investments. Increases in production volume resulting from increases in exports necessitate more employment. Another important benefit that exports provide to the country's economy and companies is in terms of competitiveness. Exporting companies face more intense competition in international markets. This competitive environment forces domestic companies to develop themselves, increase their productivity, improve their production processes and make some innovations in the production process. Therefore, due to the competitive conditions in international markets, exporting companies generally have to make more efforts to increase quality and innovate since they have to produce products that comply with international standards. In addition, naturally, thanks to exports, the country's foreign exchange revenues increase, which, as stated before, constitutes an extremely important source of income in terms of closing foreign trade deficits. In addition, the increase in the amount of foreign exchange in the country contributes to the appreciation of the national currency, the stabilization of foreign exchange rates and the establishment of the economy on a solid foundation. In addition, thanks to the increases in foreign exchange revenues, the country can easily import the goods and services required by international trade. Therefore, it is extremely important that all activities aimed at increasing export revenues are effectively supported by the state.

In its most general form, export activities are based on two pillars: export of goods and export of services. Unlike export of goods, tourism activities can be evaluated within the scope of service export. Expenditures made by tourists visiting a country contribute to the increase in foreign exchange revenues and economic development of the country, just as in export of goods. Therefore, there is a direct and strong relationship between tourism activities and export revenues. It is possible to detail this relationship between tourism activities and export of services as tourists staying at a hotel, eating at a hotel restaurant and using transportation vehicles. All of these activities are services that tourists obtain in another country, not in their own country. Therefore, tourism activities are considered as a type of export and are of a nature that earns foreign exchange for the country where the expenditure is made. The foreign exchange obtained as a result of tourism activities contributes to the reduction of the current deficit, the stabilization of the currency and the easy payment of foreign debts, as well as exports. In addition, the tourism sector activates a wide range of production activities and services, from hotel activities to transportation, from handicrafts to food production. In order to realize the increases in the production of goods and services, it is a necessity to increase employment, in other words, the revival in the tourism sector causes an increase in employment. In addition, the sale of local products to tourists in particular means a source of income and an export opportunity for local producers, which contributes to both rural development and the development of micro businesses. In addition, tourism activities allow the promotion of the country's cultural, historical and natural assets, and thus, tourists who come to a country can continue to consume products of the country they visited as a tourist when they return to their country and indirectly contribute to the increase in exports of goods by recommending these products to their close circle.

In this context, the development of tourism activities, which are extremely important for the country's economy, is of great importance. At this point, it has become extremely important to effectively utilize information technologies, one of the most important elements of today. Information technologies (IT) have become one of the main driving forces of economic, social and cultural developments today. The increasing integration of technological tools and equipment into our lives every passing day affects the activities of individuals, companies and states and causes a major transformation. The development of information technologies is extremely important in terms of both

economic growth and social development. In this context, it is possible to say that developments in information technologies contribute to economic growth, directly affect productivity growth, improve education and learning processes, and also enable globalization in the communication process and contribute to the analytical use of data. With these qualities, the effective and intensive use of information technologies in the tourism sector both contributes positively to the development of the sector and indirectly affects economic growth positively. Because of the effective use of information technologies, promotions and information for the tourism sector can be made accurately and quickly, customer satisfaction can be increased to the highest level by providing quality and comfortable services to tourists, and investments for the tourism sector increase depending on the increase in the income level. For these reasons, it is possible to say that the effective use of information technologies is extremely important for the tourism sector.

2. THE IMPORTANCE OF TOURISM IN ECONOMY

The tourism sector is one of the most important sectors for the development of national economies. The tourism sector can also be described as an industry since it includes more than one sector. The tourism industry, which consists of various infrastructures and superstructures, is a branch of the service sector and has a structure where fixed capital investments are high and is quickly affected by the economic and political context. In this respect, it is possible to say that the tourism sector makes an important contribution to the economies of both developed and developing countries, and these contributions emerge on the employment rate, national income level, balance of payments and balanced development (Kavaklı and Karakaş, 2022: 39). The tourism sector also has the feature of being a sector that affects the activation of other sectors. Because tourism activities interact with many sectors, especially the transportation sector, food sector and communication sector. Researchers have shown increasing interest in the effects of tourism in the last century. Economic effects lie at the heart of this interest. Tourism revenues, especially when it comes to the international tourism sector, provide foreign exchange input to national economies and this situation constitutes an invisible export item for countries. Therefore, the tourism sector creates direct effects on the balance of payments account of the country's economy and directly affects economic growth positively (Demir and Bahar, 2021: 162-163). Because the foreign exchange revenues obtained are directed to investments in both the tourism sector and other sectors related to the tourism sector, and increases in production volume occur. Increases in production volume directly affect economic growth and development positively. In addition, the tourism sector directly affects the communication sector, the transportation sector and the food sector, causing increases in the production volume of these sectors. Because thanks to the developments in the communication sector, tourists on the other side of the world can learn about tourism destinations, reach tourist facilities and tourism destinations thanks to the transportation sector, and have quality food and beverages thanks to the developments in the food sector.

In addition, there are increases in employment rates thanks to the tourism sector. In terms of national economies, it is possible to talk about three types of employment originating from the tourism sector: direct, indirect and additional or induced employment. Direct employment is the totality of activities performed by people working in the main and sub-branches created within the sector itself. Indirect employment is the type of employment that is carried out in sectors that do not directly include tourism factors but are formed by branches necessary for the tourism sector. Additional employment or induced employment is the type of employment created by the local people whose incomes and living standards increase due to tourism, who spend the income they earn to purchase goods and services produced both in the region and throughout the country, thus increasing the employment volume of other sectors (Örnek and Akın, 2017: 346). Increases in the number of people

employed in the tourism sector or in sectors related to the tourism sector and increases in the income levels of those employed also cause increases in demand for other sectors of the economy, new investments are made accordingly, increases in production volume occur and this process contributes to the realization of economic growth in a general sense. Therefore, due to its employment and foreign exchange generating effect, the importance of tourism is increasing day by day, new investments are being made and different strategies are being implemented by country administrators (Akyurt, 2023: 75). Within this scope, states and governments that realize the economic importance of tourism early on implement encouraging policies for the tourism sector and achieve significant economic gains.

3. IMPORTANCE OF INFORMATION TECHNOLOGIES IN TERMS OF THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE TOURISM SECTOR

Service exports have an important place in a country's external economic activities, and in this context, the tourism sector accounts for a large portion of service exports. It is possible to say that many factors have an impact on the development of the tourism sector, which is extremely important for the country's economy. One of the most important of these factors is information technologies. Information technologies (IT) play an important role in the development of tourism, and the contribution of this technology to the tourism sector is increasing day by day. In particular, digitalization allows for greater efficiency, accessibility and customer satisfaction in the tourism sector. The importance of information technologies in terms of the development of tourism can be listed under several headings, including marketing and promotion, reservation and customer relationship management, data analytics and artificial intelligence, digital infrastructure and smart tourism, and e-commerce and online payments.

3.1. Promotion and Marketing

Promotion and marketing constitute one of the most important stages of tourism activities. Because it is extremely important for people in different countries to be informed about touristic places and to be able to travel to those places, to be aware of the existence of touristic destinations and to be informed about the services they will receive in these destinations. Developments in information technologies are of great importance in this process. It is possible to say that promotional activities to be carried out nationwide are extremely important for the development of the tourism sector. Countries in a competitive market must focus on promotional activities aimed at revealing the tourism potential of the country in order to ensure and sustain the development of the tourism sector, to be ahead of their competitors and to earn more income from tourism activities. In today's world, where information can be accessed at any time and from anywhere thanks to the rapid transformation of information and technology, studies on country promotion within the scope of the opportunities offered by digitalization offer tourism businesses much more opportunities to reach potential tourists all over the world. Despite their high costs, when country promotion activities are prepared efficiently and effectively; they make significant contributions to the country's image and marketing activities. In recent years, country promotion activities have been carried out intensively through digital media (Altaş, 2017: 81). By taking advantage of the opportunities provided by information technologies, tourists are informed about touristic areas and facilities, and thus, there is a significant increase in the number of tourists visiting touristic areas.

3.2. Reservation and Customer Relations Management

Information technologies allow for the tourism sector to easily perform reservation transactions. This leads to an increase in the number of tourists and an increase in tourism activities and revenues.

One of the important features of the tourism sector is that it allows for the personalization of the service to be provided due to its structure. Therefore, providing services specific to the needs of customers plays an important role in meeting their expectations. Information technologies provide personalized suggestions to travel agencies by creating files containing customer profiles and reminding tourists of their previous preferences, thus creating both an effective customer relations management and allowing for more accurate management of the services to be provided in the sales and after-sales periods (Koçer, 2016). Collecting and evaluating the feedback of active and potential customers in travel agencies is extremely important in order to increase the quality of service and the success of customer relations management. Responding to positive or negative feedback obtained by utilizing this feedback contributes to increasing customer satisfaction and trust. Continuously improving the travel experience of customers can increase their loyalty to touristic facilities that provide service. This is possible by travel agencies creating a travel plan that is suitable for the demand. Identifying the deficiencies of the tourism sector and tourism businesses in particular and conducting solution-oriented studies strengthens customer satisfaction. In addition, the use of current information technologies facilitates reservation processes and can improve customer experience. Tools such as mobile applications and online reservation systems, which are among the opportunities of the digital age, can provide significant convenience to customers during the reservation process (Semiz Çelik, 2024: 21). In line with this information, it is possible to say that effectively utilizing the services provided by information technologies in the reservation and customer relations management process is extremely important for increasing tourism activities and tourism revenues.

3.3. Big Data Analytics, Use of Artificial Intelligence and Smart Tourism

The technologies accompanying the developments in information technologies and digital transformation help to reduce the time and effort spent on tourism activities carried out by tourism companies and to increase the quality of the service provided, while allowing tourists to choose and perform the highest quality service in the easiest and fastest way. The time savings provided by information and communication technologies that started with the digital transformation and especially the ease of storing information have become an important element for transactions in the tourism sector. (Atar, 2020: 1647-1649). In this respect, developments in information technologies and digital transformation make significant contributions to making tourism activities more efficient. The digital transformation that took place depending on the developments in information technologies means the integration of technologies such as artificial intelligence (AI) and big data (Big Data), which make tourism activities more efficient and personalize customer experiences, into the tourism sector. These technologies provide a competitive advantage to tourism businesses and play an important role in achieving the sustainability goals of businesses. Artificial intelligence is particularly prominent in the development of hotel management and customer services, while big data analytics makes significant contributions to understanding customer behavior and optimizing marketing strategies. In addition, smart destination management optimizes visitor experiences using data analytics technology, monitors tourist movements with smart traffic management, environmental sensors and sustainability applications, optimizes energy consumption and minimizes environmental impacts. In addition, thanks to virtual reality (VR) and augmented reality (AR) technologies, tourist destinations are promoted through virtual tours and tourists are provided with the opportunity to have nice experiences during their visits. In this process, digital transformation and smart tourism, which have emerged due to developments in information technologies, are shaping the future of the tourism sector, providing businesses with a competitive advantage and contributing to the achievement of sustainability goals by businesses (Gündüz, 2024: 23). For these reasons, it has become of great

importance to increase R&D activities and make the necessary investments in the tourism sector regarding the use of big data analytics, smart tourism and artificial intelligence.

3.4. E-commerce and Online Payments

In its most general form, e-commerce can be defined as the marketing and sale of tradable goods and services on the internet. Thanks to e-commerce, production, promotion, sales, insurance, distribution and payment transactions of goods and services are carried out over computer networks. Nowadays, people use the internet more effectively and consciously compared to previous periods, and accordingly, consumption activities are carried out more consciously. Today, potential tourists who want to engage in a touristic activity can gain more in-depth information by doing research on the internet before carrying out the touristic trips they plan to take, and they act accordingly by making decisions. In other words, websites that were used only for information in previous periods now increasingly affect purchasing decisions and cause the purchase of the service. As in every sector, the importance of e-commerce is increasing in the tourism sector as well. Due to the important role played by information technologies in the process of bringing together, organizing and presenting touristic goods and services to the consumer, e-commerce has become an important resource and a strategic tool in terms of providing sustainable competitive advantage for tourism businesses. E-commerce is used intensively in many different areas of the tourism sector, especially in the fields of airline management, accommodation management, travel agency, car rental, travel, promotion of tourism regions, brochure creation, catalog printing and distribution (Ateş et al. 2018: 6595). Another advantage that information technologies provide for hotel businesses is online transactions. Thanks to online transactions, reservations can be made before coming to the hotel, online payment transactions can be made, virtual tours and mobile applications that will be made online enrich the travel experience of the guests by facilitating it. (Gürsoy and Çalhan, 2024: 3). In addition, thanks to online check-in transactions, fewer staff are employed at the reception, faster service can be provided to tourists, waiting times of tourists can be shortened in in-hotel services, and it is possible to convey the satisfaction of tourists regarding the service they receive to the hotel online (Yalçınkaya et al. 2018: 91). In line with this information, it is possible to say that carrying out tourism activities in the form of e-commerce will provide significant advantages and conveniences to tourism businesses and online transactions to tourists, and this will increase tourism activities and positively affect tourism revenues.

CONCLUSION

The tourism sector is an extremely important source of wealth for countries with geographical touristic richness. It is possible to say that information technologies are extremely important in order to benefit from this source of wealth in the most efficient way economically and to increase the national income level. Because developments in information technologies make significant contributions to the development of tourism activities and directly affect the development of tourism activities at every stage. In this process, information technologies and digitalization processes are directly used at every stage of tourism activities, from promotional activities to destination and facility selection for touristic trips to be made, from reservation opportunities to payment facilities and from customer satisfaction to feedback. This contributes to the increase in tourism activities and therefore to the increase in tourism revenues. One of the most important features of the tourism sector is that it is an exporter, albeit indirectly. Because the goods and services sold to tourists during tourism activities can be considered as sold abroad, in other words, exported, since their consumers are foreign. This indirectly means that the country's export revenues increase. In addition, the

development of the tourism sector causes the sectors producing goods and services related to the tourism sector to become active and their production volumes to increase. In addition, the development of the tourism sector contributes to the increase in employment rates both in the tourism sector and in sectors that are engaged in production activities related to the tourism sector. Therefore, in order to develop the tourism sector and increase the national income level by utilizing the country's tourism potential more effectively and indirectly increase the country's export revenues, the development of information technologies in general and information technologies specifically for the tourism sector is extremely important for the country's economy. The further development of the tourism sector, which is extremely important economically today, thanks to information technologies directly contributes to the economic growth and development of the country. Because, thanks to the developments in information technologies, tourism activities become customer-oriented and sustainable, and innovative applications and solutions in the sector reach a wider audience, and these developments make significant contributions to the development of the tourism sector. Therefore, it is extremely important to increase R&D investments and expenditures for the development of information technologies and digitalization. In this way, it is possible to say that the tourism sector can develop and contribute to economic development.

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